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Distance Conversion Factors for In Situ H-field Emissions Tests

JORDI SOLÉ-LLOVERAS^{1,2}, MEMBER, IEEE, YASUTOSHI YOSHIOKA³, MEMBER, IEEE, MANUEL AÑÓN-CANCELA⁴, THILO KOOTZ⁵, FERRAN SILVA², AND MARCO A. AZPÚRUA^{1,2}, SENIOR MEMBER, IEEE

¹EMC Electromagnetic BCN, S.L. (EMC Barcelona), Barcelona, Spain

²Grup de Compatibilitat Electromagnètica, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, Barcelona, Spain

³Power System Control Research Department, Digital Innovation Laboratory, Fuji Electric Co., Ltd. Japan

⁴Instituto Nacional de Técnica Aeroespacial "Esteban Terradas" (INTA), Torrejón de Ardoz, Spain

⁵Federal Network Agency, Berlin, Germany

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR: Jordi Solé-Lloveras (e-mail: jordi.sole@emc-barcelona.com).

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ABSTRACT This paper derives and validates a set of distance conversion factors for the magnetic field emissions limits in the frequency range from 9 kHz to 30 MHz, which are intended to be proposed for their inclusion in new electromagnetic compatibility standards. Simulation models based on loop-type electromagnetic field sources are employed to evaluate, using the method of moments, the changes in the amplitude of the H-field components along the measurement axes. An algorithm is developed to extract the H-field strengths normalized to the reference distance and then, through methods for optimal detection of changepoints, such a normalized curve is fitted to a piece-wise linear function that becomes the generalized distance conversion factor, presented in the form of simplified equations. The fitness of the model is checked through experiments carried out in representative locations, showing a very good agreement between measurement and simulations. The adequacy of the conversion factors and the problem around the equipment under test are also analyzed.

INDEX TERMS conversion factors, magnetic field, in situ testing, emissions measurements, standards.

I. INTRODUCTION

MANY countries have regulations regarding electromagnetic compatibility (EMC). An example of such enforced rules is the Directive 2014/30/EU, which applies in the European market [1]. Those legal restrictions usually include requirements that electronic equipment must comply with regarding the amount of radiofrequency generated, that is, limits of electromagnetic emissions. To validate these requisites, such devices are generally tested in EMC facilities where, under controlled laboratory conditions, they are assessed following test methods defined according to international standards. However, some products cannot be evaluated in a standard EMC laboratory due to (large) size, (high) power or other constraints. In these cases, it is necessary to perform the emissions test on equipment in situ, that is, where the equipment is installed.

Some CISPR documents, such as CISPR 11 [2], CISPR 16-2-1 [3], CISPR 16-2-3 [4] and CISPR TR 16-2-5 [5], have already specified the methods for in situ radiofrequency emission measurements. In particular, CISPR 11 is the standard which specifies the limits for industrial, scientific and medical equipment. Note that this is a product family standard, which contains requirements and measurement techniques for the products of its scope.

For typical equipment, emissions from 150 kHz to 30 MHz are usually considered through the evaluation of conducted emissions. On the other hand, CISPR 11 requires that in situ emission measurements in the said frequency range shall be carried out in terms of the magnetic field strength, H , generated at a specific reference distance. In such case, limits for magnetic field strength at a reference distance of 30 m are proposed. Still, emissions measurements

performed in situ have some drawbacks. A key challenge is detecting the Equipment Under Test (EUT) emissions in the presence of ambient noise, a topic explored in [6] for which strategies based on time-domain measurements were proposed. Another problem is related to the distance between the EUT and the measuring antenna. In many cases, it is not feasible to carry out the tests at a fixed distance, i.e. 30 m, because of the limitations of the site. Besides, the greater the distance between the EUT and the measuring antenna, the higher the chances of detecting emissions from field sources different from the EUT with amplitude levels higher than the respective limits.

A solution for this is deriving conversion factors applicable to the standard emissions limits to convert them to other distances, thus allowing for more flexible in situ emissions test setups. CISPR 11 already proposes conversion factors for measurement distances greater than 30 m using an inversely proportional factor of 20 dB/dec. Such an approximated conversion factor comes from the free space path losses, which assumes far-field conditions. Nonetheless, for in situ measurement of the H-field emissions, necessarily carried out in the near field, there are no standard distance conversion factors applicable when closer measurement distances are used, even though CISPR 16-2-3 [4] gives the extrapolation method to estimate the field strength at the standard distance based on the measurements results at some distances other than the standard distance. Some factors were proposed in CISPR TR 16-4-4 [7] Annex B, but they are not openly accessible, and their formulation, validation and replication are not found in the scientific literature.

As more and more in situ emissions measurements are required (e.g. due to the exponential growth of renewable energy, such as photovoltaic systems that might be prone to generate interference), a new standard project identified as CISPR 37 [8] is promoted to fill those technical gaps. CISPR 37 is under development with the participation of a wide group of technical experts in the framework of the CIS\B\WG7; some are coauthors in this paper. CISPR 37 focuses exclusively on in situ electromagnetic emissions testing. Proposals for CISPR 37 include defining the reference distance at 10 m, the allowance of measurement distances starting from 3 m and distance conversion factors for the H-field emissions limits from 150 kHz to 30 MHz.

This paper derives and validates a set of distance conversion factors for the H-field emissions limits for frequencies below 30 MHz, which are intended to be proposed for their inclusion in CISPR 37. Even though the lower frequency range defined for limits is 150 kHz, it is decided to broaden such range from 9 kHz for a possible later extension of the limits towards lower frequencies.

The in situ problem, as well as the motivation to find the factor, are formally formulated in Section II. Then, electromagnetic simulations based on loop-type source are used to evaluate the variation in the amplitude of the H-field components as we move over measurement

axes (Section III). The correctness of the model is checked through two independent experiments carried out in representative locations, showing very good agreement between measurement and simulations (Section IV). Then, an algorithm is developed to extract the H-field strengths normalized to the reference distance. Such a normalized curve is fitted to a piece-wise linear function that becomes the generalized distance conversion factor (Section V). Finally, the paper concludes with some final remarks about the prospective of in situ emissions measurement methods and standards.

II. PROBLEM DEFINITION

For an in situ emission test, the measuring antenna is placed at a measuring distance, d_m , from the reference point around the EUT for each measurement axes. Ideally, measures are taken at the reference distance, d_{ref} , the distance at which the emissions limit is defined by the corresponding standard. In most cases, $d_m \neq d_{ref}$ because of restrictions of the perimeter of the test site as shown in Fig. 1.

FIGURE 1. Top view of a typical in situ situation. At the n -th point, measures are conducted at a distance $d_{m,n}$. Some of the axis allow measures at the reference distance, d_{ref} , while others require measuring at different distances.

Measuring emissions at shorter distances might be convenient to identify emission sources. On the other hand, measuring distances larger than reference distance are necessary. For example, in extremely large EUTs (i.e. wind turbines) or when shorter distances are inaccessible (for example, when a road is in the way).

Hence, if $d_m \neq d_{ref}$, conversion factors, $CF(d_m, d_{ref}, f)$, are needed to set the standard emission limits at a d_{ref} , $L_{ref}(f)$, to the actual measuring distance d_m , as given by,

$$L_m(f) = L_{ref}(f) + CF(d_m, d_{ref}, f), \quad (1)$$

where $L_m(f)$ is the equivalent limit at d_m . Both limits are expressed in dB μ A/m.

Such conversion factors must consider the variation of field strength with distance and the influence of the orientation of the source. In this specific case and frequency range, the focus is on the emissions in terms of absolute magnetic field strength expressed in decibel units (dB μ A/m). Therefore, conversion factors will depend on the ratio of the field, Δ' , between two arbitrary points P_{ref} and P_m :

$$\Delta'(P_m, P_{ref}, f) = H_m(f) - H_{ref}(f), \quad (2)$$

where H_m and H_{ref} are the field strength levels at points P_m and P_{ref} , respectively. P_m and P_{ref} are determined by the distance with respect to the EUT boundary, the orientation of the measurement axis, and the height of the antenna, h .

Regarding this, the H-field emissions depend on the type of source and change from EUT to EUT. Such emissions can be represented as a combination of fundamental magnetic and electric field sources. Nonetheless, for simplicity, it is decided to use a loop antenna as the source model to calculate the H-field distribution. Previous discussions held at the referenced technical working groups support such a compromise criterion.

Based on the model of a standard 60 cm loop antenna [9] proposed in Fig. 2, the ratios on x - and y -axes can be derived from (2) and, in Cartesian coordinates, are defined as:

$$\Delta_X(d_m, d_{ref}, f) = H(d_m, 0, h, f) - H(d_{ref}, 0, h, f), \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta_Y(d_m, d_{ref}, f) = H(0, d_m, h, f) - H(0, d_{ref}, h, f), \quad (4)$$

where $d_{ref} = 10$ m is assumed throughout all the document. As measures are conducted typically in the x - y plane, ratio associated to z -axis is not considered.

$CF(d_m, d_{ref}, f)$ shall be a single set of factors, that apply to H-field emissions limits independently of the antenna orientation. Therefore, CF must consider both Δ_X and Δ_Y . The ratios Δ_X and Δ_Y are simulated and validated in Section III and IV, respectively. Then, the algorithm to extract the conversion factors is presented in Section V.

III. SIMULATIONS

The method of moments is used to compute the electromagnetic field using MATLAB and 4nec2 solvers. The simulation has been performed at 1000 equally log-spaced frequency points from 9 kHz to 30 MHz and at various distances from 3 m to 100 m.

The simulation model is a circular loop with a diameter of 60 cm oriented in x -axis as shown in Fig. 2. The source is located at $(0, 0, h)$ and the height from the ground plane to the center of the antenna is $h = 1.3$ m. For each condition, the E-field and H-field at a single point are recorded along the x - and y -axis

Fig. 3 presents Δ_X and Δ_Y for $d_m = 3$ m and Fig. 4 shows the results at $d_m = 30$ m. The selection of such example distances is not arbitrary. First of all, 3 m is selected as the shortest measurement distance typically used during radiated emissions tests in a standard test site. On the other hand, 30 m is picked due to the [2] legacy as the distance at which the magnetic field limits are defined. It is

FIGURE 2. Simulation model with the defined axis. The ground plane is modelled as an infinite and perfect electric conductor.

important to consider that, at such a distance and depending on the equipment type and topology and ambient field level conditions, the EUT emissions might not be detectable.

FIGURE 3. Ratios obtained in the x - and y -axis for $d_m = 3$ m.

FIGURE 4. Ratios obtained in x - and y -axis for $d_m = 30$ m.

It is observed how, as the frequency increases, the ratios show a transition from near-field to far-field. Such frequency

dependence for each distance should be considered when designing the conversion factor extraction algorithm.

IV. MODEL VALIDATION

The simulation model for Δ_X is validated experimentally throughout two different Δ_X measurement campaigns that are described in what follows. Considering the intrinsic characteristics of the small loop, the validation of Δ_Y in an open area is omitted due to high levels of ambient noise.

A. Experiment 1: 100 kHz - 2 MHz

In the first experiment, an R&S HFH2-Z2E broadband active loop antenna is used as the receiving element. For the transmitter, two loops of different sizes are built, one with a dimension of 0.75 m x 0.75 m and a larger one with a dimension of 1.5 m x 1.5 m. The center of both loops respect to ground is at $1.3 \text{ m} \pm 5 \text{ cm}$ and they are located at a distance d_m from the receiver antenna as depicted in Fig. 5.

FIGURE 5. Simplified diagram of Experiment 1 setup.

The receiving antenna has a fixed position to keep an ambient noise level as similar and repetitive as possible during the experiment. An example photo of the experiment is shown in Fig. 6.

FIGURE 6. Experiment 1. The measuring antenna and the 1.5 m x 1.5 m loop are shown.

In the transmission end, chirp pulses are injected to cover the range from 100 kHz to 2 MHz. In reception, a custom time domain measurement system (emiGO™ by EMC Barcelona) is used, which is based on a general-purpose oscilloscope (Picoscope 5444D MSO) connected to a computer with its own software that calculates the spectrum

in compliance with existing standards. The resolution bandwidth is according to CISPR 16. The sampling rate is 250 MSa/s, the resolution is 12-bit, and the acquisition time is 1 s per chirp. Results of the H-field recorded at several distances are displayed in Fig. 7.

FIGURE 7. Recorded magnetic field at different distances in Experiment 1. Ambient noise is depicted as a black trace.

To obtain Δ_X , the field strength level at each distance for $f = 1 \text{ MHz}$ is recorded and normalized with the field strength level at 10 m. Δ_X obtained with two different sizes of transmitting loops are practically equal below 2 MHz.

B. Experiment 2: 1 MHz - 30 MHz

The purpose of the second experiment is to cover the range from 1 MHz up to 30 MHz. This time, the transmitting antenna is a passive loop Schwarzbeck HFRA 5149 and the receiver loop is a broadband loop Schwarzbeck FMBZ 1519B. Antenna height (from the center to ground) is 1.3 m. Acquisition settings are the same as Experiment 1. A photo of the experiments is shown in Fig. 8.

FIGURE 8. Experiment 2. The open area test site and the transmitting and receiving antennas are depicted.

In this case, ambient levels measured are shown in Fig. 9, and frequencies of 1 MHz, 5 MHz, 10 MHz, 20 MHz and 30 MHz are selected for the experiment. In those frequencies, no emissions from other devices or nearby communication systems were present. A sinusoidal signal of same level was injected to an amplifier connected to the transmitting

antenna. For each frequency and distance, the level obtained at the receiving antenna is recorded. Then, H-field levels are normalized to a reference distance of 10 m in order to extract the ratios Δ_X .

FIGURE 9. Experiment 2. Ambient magnetic field noise level.

C. Results

This section presents the results from experimental validation compared with the obtained in the simulation. The Δ_X ratio is compared as a function of distance for five specific frequencies. In Fig. 10, the results of Experiment 1, Experiment 2 and simulations at 1 MHz are shown.

The lowest frequency considered is 1 MHz, which is below the corner frequency in all simulated cases. We can see that Experiment 1 fits the simulation excellently, with a small divergence at high distances (higher than 25 m). These results allow us to validate the model at this frequency. A larger divergence is seen in the performance of Experiment 2. This may be due to the actual efficiency of using smaller transmission and reception antennas (50 cm each). However, such a deviation is in the order of magnitude of tolerable uncertainties in typical EMC tests.

At 5 MHz, 10 MHz, 20 MHz and 30 MHz the results are the obtained from Experiment 2. Comparisons are shown in Fig. 11 to Fig. 14, respectively.

FIGURE 10. Simulation versus experimental results at 1 MHz.

FIGURE 11. Simulation versus experimental results at 5 MHz.

FIGURE 12. Simulation versus experimental results at 10 MHz.

FIGURE 13. Simulation versus experimental results at 20 MHz.

At frequencies from 5 MHz to 20 MHz, a better correspondence is observed. In the upper range of 30 MHz, simulations and experiments overlap from 7 m to 30 m, but a small discrepancy can be noticed at shorter distances. These effects are due to the practical and real characteristics of the antennas and the equipment and cables used to generate the transmission. However, having validated most of the frequencies and distances, we consider the simulation model to be adequate and consistent with the experiments.

FIGURE 14. Simulation versus experimental results at 30 MHz.

The measurement uncertainty has been estimated for the experimental validation. Since the receiving antenna factor and cable attenuation do not change with the antenna position, the ratio Δ_X in terms of H-field is equivalent to the ratios calculated using the voltage level at the antenna port, V . Therefore, the model of the measurement system, with all quantities in decibel units, is according to (5),

$$V = V_{QP} + \delta_a + \delta_{step} + \delta_d + \delta_h, \quad (5)$$

where V_{QP} is the voltage level detected using the FFT-based measuring receiver in quasi-peak (QP) mode, and its variations represent the measurement repetitiveness; δ_a corresponds to the sine wave voltage level tolerances of the instrument in the given frequency range, δ_{step} is the error due to a limited frequency resolution of the spectrum, and δ_d and δ_h are the readings variation due to imprecise antenna positioning in the horizontal and vertical plane.

Table 1 presents the uncertainty budget for V , indicating the type of evaluation used for each contribution, their estimated value and the probability distribution assigned to each. In this case, all uncertainty contributions are considered independent, and their mean values are 0 dB. The standard uncertainties are combined directly in decibel units following the guidelines in CISPR 16-4-2 [10]. This approximation is deemed acceptable when the values are small in order to avoid asymmetrical intervals for the combined uncertainty.

TABLE 1. Uncertainty budget for the measurement of the received voltage.

Contribution factors		Standard deviation	Probability distribution		Standard uncertainty	Unit
Type	Source of uncertainty		Function	Divisor		
A	Receiver reading, V_{QP}	0,20	Normal ($k=1$)	1,00	0,20	dB
B	Level accuracy, δ_a	0,50	Normal ($k=2$)	2,00	0,25	dB
B	Freq. resolution, δ_{step}	0,37	Rectangular	1,73	0,21	dB
B	Antenna distance, δ_d	0,40	Rectangular	1,73	0,23	dB
B	Antenna height, δ_h	0,10	Rectangular	1,73	0,06	dB
Combined standard uncertainty =					$\pm 0,45$	dB
Expanded uncertainty ~95 % ($k=2$) =					$\pm 0,90$	dB

Concerning the evaluation of the uncertainty, for Type A sources, we performed multiple repetitions of the measurement, and the standard deviation was calculated with

degrees of freedom equal to 29. The Type B sources related to the instrument are evaluated using information from calibration certificates, while those regarding the antenna position are estimated using simulation.

Finally, given the measured field ratios require two voltage measurements, then the expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$) of Δ_X is estimated in ± 1.3 dB.

V. CONVERSION FACTORS

In this section, a conversion factor based on the obtained ratios Δ_X and Δ_Y will be proposed. Firstly, we address the problem of combining Δ_X and Δ_Y in such a way we can extract a single ratio, Δ_C . Then, straightforward procedure is presented in order to convert Δ_C to final piece-wise conversion factors, CF . Such procedure is necessary in order to simplify the implementation of factors in corresponding standards. Finally, CF for several distances are summarized in form of a table. Note that Δ_C and CF will depend on d_m , d_{ref} , and f .

A. COMBINATION OF Δ_X AND Δ_Y

In a real situation, the orientation of the source with respect to the measurement axis is unknown, as well as the direction of the maximum emissions. This should be considered when combining Δ_X and Δ_Y in order to prevent an unintended relaxation of the emission requirements after the application of the conversion factors. This is important because the level of protection to radio services should be guaranteed.

To analyze this phenomenon, the magnetic field obtained around a small loop source at a hypothetical distance of 10 m (reference distance) is simulated (Fig. 15) for a single frequency. In other words, the magnetic field is sensed around the EUT and the field strength is plotted as a function of the measurement axis azimuth angle, being 0° the orientation of the maximum amplitude. Then, a hypothetical limit is set at the median value of the field strength in order to have 50% of measurement points that exceed the limit and 50% of measurement points that are below. From another point of view, if we take a single measurement on a random axis, we would have the same probability of determining whether the equipment is compliant or non-compliant.

Then, it is considered that it is not possible to measure at the reference distance set by the limit, 10 m, so the measurements are conducted at, for example, $d_m = 3$ m. Consequently, the limit has to be corrected by applying some conversion factors, CF . Let us assume that $CF = \Delta_C$. Fig. 16 shows the corrected limit calculated according the two definitions of Δ_C listed below:

- 1) $\Delta_{C1} = \Delta_X$, because the x component is dominant when the source is an elemental magnetic loop, as shown in Fig. 2.
- 2) $\Delta_{C2} = \min(\Delta_X, \Delta_Y)$, considering the dominant component of the H-field vector is unknown.

FIGURE 15. H-field strength around a small loop source at 10 m from its center and 1.3 m height. The median of the field strength is used as a hypothetical emissions limit. Therefore, if a single measurement axis is randomly selected over the EUT plane, the probability that the EUT emissions are found to be above the limit is 50%.

FIGURE 16. H-field strength around a small loop source above a ground plane at 3 m from its center and 1.3 m height. The limit used at 10 m in Fig. 15 is converted to the measurement distance using Δ_{C1} and Δ_{C2} .

After applying the conversion factors according to the first definition (Δ_{C1}), only 23.52% of the points at 3 m are above the limit, which signifies a higher risk of not detecting that the emissions are exceeding the limit with respect to the original case. Using Δ_{C2} , 90.28% of possible points around the EUT exceed the limit. From the previous results, it is clear that approach (2) provides protection levels that are more likely to deliver the correct conclusions of the emission test.

This analysis has been extended in terms of frequency and distances, assuming that the reference distance, d_{ref} , is 10 m, where the probability is 50%. In other words, the former simulation has been repeated for the whole frequency range under study and distances from 3 m to 10 m. Then, the probability of exceeding the limit is represented. The results applying Δ_{C1} and Δ_{C2} are shown in Fig. 17 and Fig. 18 respectively.

The straight green line at 10 m for all frequencies is where no conversion factors are applied, and it indicates

FIGURE 17. Probability of exceeding the limits of a small loop type of source when applying $CF = \Delta_{C1}$ for $d_{ref} = 10$ m.

FIGURE 18. Probability of exceeding the limits of a small loop type of source when applying $CF = \Delta_{C2}$ for $d_{ref} = 10$ m.

a probability of 50%. In Fig. 17, it is confirmed that an incorrect definition of the conversion factor may lead to a significant relaxation of the emissions requirement, which is not desirable. On the other hand, in the case of Fig. 18, applying the conversion factors increases the likelihood of detecting that the EUT emissions are above the applicable limit.

Therefore, it is proposed to define as,

$$\Delta_C = \min(\Delta_X, \Delta_Y). \quad (6)$$

Nonetheless, there should be a symmetry between the factors applied when approaching the source or when departing from the source. That means the dependence of Δ_C on d_m , d_{ref} and f as $\Delta_C(d_m, d_{ref}, f)$ must satisfy the condition,

$$\Delta_C(d_1, d_2, f) = -\Delta_C(d_2, d_1, f), \quad (7)$$

where d_1 and d_2 are arbitrary distances. To fulfill this requirement, the final Δ_C is defined as,

$$\Delta_C = \text{sgn}(\Delta_X) \min(|\Delta_X|, |\Delta_Y|). \quad (8)$$

B. PIECE-WISE FACTOR EXTRACTION

The conversion factor at a given distance d_m , $CF(d_m, d_{ref}, f)$, must be straightforward to apply, as well as allow a feasible integration into the standards. Thus, the function that describes the factor, which will be

dependent on distance and frequency, must be expressed as simply as possible. Therefore, it is proposed to approximate Δ_C through a combination of piece-wise linear functions, $CF_i(f)$ as shown in (9). For sake of simplicity, the dependence of d_m and d_{ref} is omitted in the notation.

$$CF(f) = \sum_{i=1}^{k+1} CF_i(f), \quad (9)$$

where $CF_i(f)$ is the equation of a straight line defined between a pair of changepoints occurring at discrete frequencies φ_{i-1} and φ_i . In other words,

$$CF_i(f) = \begin{cases} \alpha_i f + \beta_i & \text{for } \varphi_{i-1} < f \leq \varphi_i \\ 0 & \text{for } f \leq \varphi_{i-1} \vee f > \varphi_i \end{cases}. \quad (10)$$

To extract φ_i , changepoint analysis is carried out following the methodology in [11]. This involves identifying points within a dataset where specific statistical properties change. These properties can include the standard deviation, the root mean square (RMS) level, the mean value, or the slope.

Assuming each section of the conversion factors is represented by an ordered sequence of sampled data points $\Delta_{C,1:n} = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n\}$, each point corresponding to the frequencies $F_{1:n} = \{f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n\}$, and that it is of interest to fit $(f_{1:n}; \Delta_{C,1:n})$ according to the model in (9) and (10) for $k+1$ piece-wise linear segments. This requires to find k optimal changepoints, $cp_{1:k}$, each of them must be calculated to segment the dataset according to abrupt changes in the mean value and slope. These changepoints occur at discrete frequencies $\varphi_{1:k} = \{\varphi_1, \varphi_2, \dots, \varphi_k\}$. Each changepoint discrete frequency corresponds to a vector position that is an integer between 1 and $n-1$ inclusive.

We define $\varphi_0 = f_1$ and $\varphi_{k+1} = f_n$ and assume that the changepoints are ordered such that $\varphi_i < \varphi_j$ if, and only if, $i < j$. Consequently, the k changepoints will split the dataset into $k+1$ segments, with the i -th segment containing $P_{(\varphi_{i-1}):\varphi_i}$.

One commonly used approach to identify multiple changepoints is to minimize (11),

$$\sum_{i=1}^{k+1} [\kappa_i(\Delta_{C,(\varphi_{i-1}):\varphi_i})] + g(k), \quad (11)$$

where $\kappa_i(\cdot)$ is the cost function for the i -th segment and $g(k)$ is a penalty to guard against overfitting. For linear cost functions, the PELT (Pruned Exact Linear Time) method is computationally efficient for finding the changepoints. More about the PELT method and other algorithms for solving the previous equation are reviewed in [12].

Regarding the cost function in (11), a suitable choice is the sum of squared errors, SSE , as it measures the goodness of fit of regression models. The SSE of the i -th segment is given by,

$$SSE_i = \sum_{j=1}^m (a_{j,i} - CF_i(f_{j,i}))^2, \quad (12)$$

where $(f_{j,i}; a_{j,i})$ is the frequency-amplitude coordinate of the j -th point of the i -th segment, with that segment

containing m samples. A small SSE indicates a tight fit of the model to the data.

Then, the best linear fit of the subset of m points in the i -th segment $\Delta_{C,(\varphi_{i-1}):\varphi_i}$ is obtained through the least squares regression, that is,

$$\alpha_i = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^m (\bar{a}_i - a_{j,i}) (\bar{f}_i - f_{j,i})}{\sum_{j=1}^m (\bar{f}_i - f_{j,i})^2}, \quad (13)$$

$$\beta_i = \bar{a}_i - \alpha_i \bar{f}_i, \quad (14)$$

where α_i and β_i are the slope coefficient and the intercept of the i -th segment in (10), respectively, and \bar{a}_i and \bar{f}_i are the mean values of the amplitudes and their corresponding frequencies, respectively.

Therefore, a piecewise factor for $k=2$ (3 sections) is calculated employing the former algorithm implemented through the *findchangepts* [13], [14] MATLAB function. In this particular case, $\varphi_0 = 9$ kHz, $\varphi_3 = 30$ MHz and φ_1 and φ_2 are the variable corner frequencies that depend on d_m . Fig. 19 and Fig. 20 show examples of the algorithm output for $d_m = 3$ m and $d_m = 30$ m, respectively.

FIGURE 19. Output of the piece-wise factor extraction algorithm. $d_m=3$ m.

FIGURE 20. Output of the piece-wise factor extraction algorithm. $d_m=30$ m.

The approximation error, defined as the difference between Δ_C and CF , is calculated for the full range of frequencies and distances from 3 m to 100 m. The distribution of such error is presented as a histogram (Fig. 21). It is found that for 70% of the points, the error is within ± 0.5 dB while for 95% of cases, the error is better than ± 3 dB and finally, for 99.8% of the points the error is kept less than ± 6 dB.

FIGURE 21. Approximation error of the linear piece-wise factors.

C. RESULTS

Distance conversion factors assuming a $d_{ref} = 10$ m are presented on Table 2 and on Fig. 22. For the interpretation of the conversion factors proposed, it is important to realize that a positive value means the emissions limit increases as we approach the source. Conversely, negative values indicate the limit decreases as we move further away from the EUT.

TABLE 2. Distance conversion factors for in situ H-field emissions measurements. The reference distance is 10 m. The range of measurement distances is from 3 m to 100 m.

Measurement distance m	Corner frequency ϕ_1 MHz	Corner frequency ϕ_2 MHz	Extrapolation factor (dB)		
			9 kHz to ϕ_1	ϕ_1 to ϕ_2	ϕ_2 to 30 MHz
3	3.7	11.3	26.8	$48.0 - 37.3 \log(f)$	8.6
4	3.3	9.5	20.5	$36.3 - 30.4 \log(f)$	6.6
5	3.0	8.2	15.5	$26.9 - 23.8 \log(f)$	5.0
6	2.8	7.4	11.4	$19.4 - 18.0 \log(f)$	3.8
7	2.6	6.8	7.9	$13.2 - 12.6 \log(f)$	2.6
8	2.4	6.4	4.9	$7.9 - 7.8 \log(f)$	1.7
9	2.3	6.0	2.3	$3.7 - 3.7 \log(f)$	0.8
15	1.9	4.6	-10.3	$-15.3 + 18.4 \log(f)$	-3.2
20	1.6	4.2	-17.7	$-23.8 + 29.4 \log(f)$	-5.6
25	1.5	3.9	-23.4	$-29.5 + 37.4 \log(f)$	-7.5
30	1.4	3.7	-28.1	$-34.0 + 43.9 \log(f)$	-9.1
50	1.3	3.5	-41.0	$-49.8 + 67.4 \log(f)$	-13.5
70	1.0	3.2	-49.7	$-50.6 + 67.1 \log(f)$	-16.5
100	0.8	3.0	-58.8	$-51.4 + 65.9 \log(f)$	-19.8

In the frequency range ϕ_1 to ϕ_2 , the correction factor is calculated using the provided formula, where f is the frequency in MHz. Function log is defined as logarithm function in base-10.

FIGURE 22. Distance conversion factors for in situ H-field emissions tests in the frequency range from 9 kHz to 30 MHz.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, distance conversion factors are obtained for magnetic field limits in the range from 9 kHz to 30 MHz. These factors are experimentally validated with very good agreement throughout the frequency range considered.

A reference distance of 10 m is proposed instead of the historically used one of 30 m. The measurement of magnetic field at shorter distances, especially when the tests are conducted in situ, is advantageous as it allows the detection of the emissions of the EUT with higher field strengths with respect to typical ambient noise levels. However, it is also necessary to provide factors at larger distances in cases where the equipment is very large or consists of many modules. It is also important to provide factors at shorter distances in the case that, due to test site limitations, it is not possible to measure at the distance required by the standard.

A mathematical algorithm was designed to automate the extraction of the said conversion factors and to provide a piece-wise function that allows the factors to be applied in a simple and practical way.

Finally, it is important to consider the proposed factor definition does not relax the current radio protection requirements set by the CISPR. However, after the application of the proposed limits, when assessing an equipment at $d_m < d_{ref}$, the converted limits might be more restrictive at some frequencies with respect to a situation when measuring at $d_m > d_{ref}$. This should be understood when using distance conversion factors as part of the emissions compliance assessment.

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JORDI SOLÉ-LLOVERAS (Member, IEEE) holds a BSc degree in telecommunication engineering (2020) and an MSc degree in electronics engineering (2022), both from Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC). He is pursuing a PhD in electronics engineering at the same university. In 2018 he joined the Grup de Compatibilitat Electromagnètica (GCEM) of the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya. In the GCEM group, he has been involved in testing

and technology transfer projects with private companies. In addition, he has participated in different research projects in collaboration with EU partners. Since 2021 he has worked at EMC Barcelona, a company dedicated to electromagnetic compatibility in which he participates in R&D projects and leads many tasks oriented to this field.

YASUTOSHI YOSHIOKA (Member, IEEE) received the PhD in electrical engineering from the Kyushu Institute of Technology, Japan, in 2006. Since 1993, he has worked at Fuji Electric Company Ltd. in R&D on EMC, power quality, and grid connection for distributed energy resources. He was a visiting scientist at the Univ. of Toronto from 1999 to 2002 and at Tokyo City University in 2009. Since 2016, he has been a visiting researcher with AIST. Since 2008, he has been involved in international standardization

under the IEC and received the IEC 1906 Award in 2014 and 2022.

MANUEL AÑÓN-CANCELA received the M.Sc degree in physics from Universidade de Santiago de Compostela in 1989. He joined the Instituto Nacional de Técnica Aeroespacial (INTA) in 1991 as an E3 engineer in the EMC Area, being involved in several national and international projects for the aerospace and defence sectors. He is currently the Head of the EMC at INTA. He is a member of national and international standardization groups for military and civilian E3 specs.

THILO KOOTZ received the MSc degree in physics from the Univ. of Cologne in 1997 focussing on Astro- and Molecular Physics with orientation on Submm-Wave Radio Telescopes. Later, he researched precise calibration techniques of VNAs at PTB until 2003. He worked in human exposure limitation to EMF until 2006, when he got involved in radioprotection and joined the IEC/CISPR. Currently, he is the chair of CISPR/H. In 2017, he joined the Federal Network Agency in Germany, continuing his work in EMC

standardization. He received the 1906 award from IEC in 2016.

FERRAN SILVA received the MSc and PhD degrees from the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC), Barcelona, Spain, in 1989 and 1997, respectively. He is Associate Professor at the Dept. of Electronic Engineering, UPC. Since 1993, he is Head of the EMC Group at UPC (GCEM). His research interests are EMC in the near field and time domain, with applications to transport, medical and industrial areas. F. Silva has more than 140 papers about EMC in journals and conferences. He has participated in 32 R&D

projects related to EMC. Furthermore, he is also a member of the EMC Spanish Standardization Committees SCTC77-210 and the CTN208. He was Chairman in 2006 and 2019 of the EMC Europe International Symposium editions in Barcelona. From 2021 to 2024, he chaired the EMC Europe ISC.

MARCO A. AZPÚRUA (Senior Member, IEEE) received a BSc in telecom. (2008) and an MSc in electrical engineering (2013) from the Univ. Central de Venezuela. In 2018, obtained a PhD in Electronics from the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC), Spain, for his contributions to Time-Domain EMI measurements. Currently, he works as an Assoc. Prof. at UPC. Dr. Azpúrua is the Co-founder of EMC Barcelona, a fellow of the StandICT.eu (2023/2026) projects and a member of the CISPR/CIS/B/WG 1 & WG 7, the IEEE

EMC and IMS societies, and the IEEE/ICES. He received the IEEE Inst. and Meas. Society Faculty Course Development Award in 2020, the UPC Special Doctoral Award for the Best Thesis in the field of Electronics, and the Best Student Paper Award in the 2017 EMC Europe.